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Multidimensional Laguerre Transform and Modified of generalized multivariable A -function

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Abstract :

The object of this paper is to use the multidimensional Laguerre transforms involving the modified of generalized multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function. In the end, we shall see several corollaries and remarks.

Keywords : Generalized of modified multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function, modified multivariable A -function, generalized A -function, multivariable A -function, multivariable I -function, multivariable H -function, multiple integral contours, multidimensional Laguerre transforms.

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1. Introduction and Preliminaries :

Chandel and Chauhan [3] have introduced a new multidimensional Laguerre integral recently, they have calculated the image of multivariable H -function

[14]

defined by Srivastava and Panda [13, 14] and generalized multiple hypergeometric functions by this multidimensional integral operator. The aim of this paper is to calculate the image of the modified of generalized multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function by this multidimensional integral transforms.

In this section, we define and study the generalized of modified multivariable A -function by using the multiple Mellin-Barnes integrals contour.

$$\bar{A}(z_1, \dots, z_r) = \bar{A}_{P, Q; R: P_1, q_1; \dots; P_r, q_r}^{M, N; R': m_1, n_1; \dots; m_r, n_r} \left(\begin{matrix} z_1 \\ \vdots \\ z_r \end{matrix} \left| \begin{matrix} (a_j; \alpha_j^{(1)}, \dots, \alpha_j^{(r)}; A_j)_{1, P} \\ (b_j; \beta_j^{(1)}, \dots, \beta_j^{(r)}; B_j)_{1, Q} \\ (e_j; u_j' g_j', \dots, u_j^{(r)} g_j^{(r)}; E_j)_{1, R'}: (c_j^{(1)}; \gamma_j^{(1)}; C_j^{(1)})_{1, p_1}, \dots, (c_j^{(r)}; \gamma_j^{(r)}; C_j^{(r)})_{1, p_r} \\ (l_j; U_j' f_j', \dots, U_j^{(r)} f_j^{(r)}; L_j)_{1, R}: (d_j^{(1)}; \delta_j^{(1)}; D_j^{(1)})_{1, q_1}, \dots, (d_j^{(r)}; \delta_j^{(r)}; D_j^{(r)})_{1, q_r} \end{matrix} \right. \right)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^r} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_r} \phi(t_1, \dots, t_r) \prod_{i=1}^r \theta_i(t_i) z_i^{t_i} dt_1 \dots dt_r \tag{1.1}$$

where $\phi(t_1, \dots, t_r), \theta_i(t_i), i = 1, \dots, r$ are given by :

$$\phi(t_1, \dots, t_r) = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^M \Gamma^{B_j}(b_j - \sum_{i=1}^r \beta_j^{(i)} t_i) \prod_{j=1}^N \Gamma^{A_j}(1 - a_j + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_j^{(i)} t_i)}{\prod_{j=N+1}^P \Gamma^{A_j}(a_j - \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_j^{(i)} t_i) \prod_{j=M+1}^Q \Gamma^{B_j}(1 - b_j + \sum_{i=1}^r \beta_j^{(i)} t_i)} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{R'} \Gamma^{E_j}(e_j + \sum_{i=1}^r u_j^{(i)} g_j^{(i)} t_i)}{\prod_{j=1}^R \Gamma^{L_j}(l_j + \sum_{i=1}^r U_j^{(i)} f_j^{(i)} t_i) \tag{1.2}$$

$$\theta_i(t_i) = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{n_i} \Gamma^{C_j^{(i)}}(1 - c_j^{(i)} + \gamma_j^{(i)} t_i) \prod_{j=1}^{m_i} \Gamma^{D_j^{(i)}}(d_j^{(i)} - \delta_j^{(i)} t_i)}{\prod_{j=n_i+1}^{p_i} \Gamma^{C_j^{(i)}}(c_j^{(i)} - \gamma_j^{(i)} t_i) \prod_{j=m_i+1}^{q_i} \Gamma^{D_j^{(i)}}(1 - d_j^{(i)} + \delta_j^{(i)} t_i) \tag{1.3}$$

Here $M, N, P, Q, R, R', m_i, n_i, p_i, c_i \in \mathbf{N}^*$; $i = 1, \dots, r$; $a_j, b_j, e_j, l_j, c_j^{(i)}, d_j^{(i)}, \alpha_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)}, \gamma_j^{(i)}, \delta_j^{(i)}, f_j^{(i)}, g_j^{(i)} \in \mathbf{C}$ and $A_i, B_i, E_i, L_i, C_j^{(i)}, D_j^{(i)}$ are positive real numbers.

The contour L_i is in the $t_i (i = 1, \dots, r)$ - plane and run from $\sigma - i\infty$ to $\sigma + i\infty$, where σ if is a real number with loop, if necessary to ensure that the poles of $\Gamma^{A_j}(1 - a_j + \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha_j^{(i)} t_i)$, $(j = 1, \dots, N)$, $\Gamma^{C_j^{(i)}}(1 - c_j^{(i)} + \gamma_j^{(i)} t_i)$, $(j = 1, \dots, n_i)$, $(i = 1, \dots, r)$ to the left of the contour L_i and the poles of $\Gamma^{B_j}(b_j - \sum_{i=1}^r \beta_j^{(i)} t_i)$, $(j = 1, \dots, M)$, $\Gamma^{D_j^{(i)}}(d_j^{(i)} - \delta_j^{(i)} t_i)$, $(j = 1, \dots, m_i)$, $(i = 1, \dots, r)$ lie to the right of the contour L_i . The poles of the integrand are assumed to be simple. Also the pole of $\Gamma^{E_j}(e_j + \sum_{i=1}^r u_i^{(i)} g_j^{(i)} t_i)$ lie to the left or right of it according $u_j^{(i)}$ is positive or negative. The various parameters being restricted so that these poles of the integrand are assumed to be simple. The point $z_i = 0 (i = 1, \dots, r)$ being tacitly excluded.

The multiple integrals defining the modified of generalized $\bar{A}$ -function of r variables converges absolutely if :

$$|\arg(\Omega_i)z_i| < \frac{1}{2} \eta_i \pi, \xi_i^* = 0, \eta_i > 0 \tag{1.4}$$

$$\Omega_i = \prod_{j=1}^P \{\alpha_j^{(i)} A_j\}^{A_j \alpha_j^{(i)}} \prod_{j=1}^Q \{\beta_j^{(i)} B_j\}^{-\beta_j^{(i)} B_j} \prod_{j=1}^{q_i} \{\delta_j^{(i)} D_j^{(i)}\}^{\delta_j^{(i)} D_j^{(i)}} \prod_{j=1}^{p_i} \{\gamma_j^{(i)} C_j^{(i)}\}^{-\gamma_j^{(i)} C_j^{(i)}} \prod_{j=1}^R \{L_j f_j^{(i)}\}^{-L_j f_j^{(i)}} \tag{1.5}$$

$$\xi_i^* = \text{Im} \left(\sum_{j=1}^P \alpha_j^{(i)} A_j - \sum_{j=1}^Q \beta_j^{(i)} B_j + \sum_{j=1}^R f_j^{(i)} L_j + \sum_{j=1}^{q_i} D_j^{(i)} \delta_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=1}^{p_i} C_j^{(i)} \gamma_j^{(i)} \right); i = 1, \dots, r \tag{1.6}$$

$$\eta_i = \text{Re} \left(\sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_j^{(i)} A_j - \sum_{j=N+1}^P \alpha_j^{(i)} A_j + \sum_{j=1}^M \beta_j^{(i)} B_j - \sum_{j=M+1}^Q \beta_j^{(i)} B_j + \sum_{j=1}^{m_i} \delta_j^{(i)} D_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=m_i+1}^{q_i} \delta_j^{(i)} D_j^{(i)} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \gamma_j^{(i)} C_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=n_i+1}^{p_i} \gamma_j^{(i)} C_j^{(i)} + \sum_{j=1}^{R'} E_j g_j^{(i)} - \sum_{j=1}^R L_j f_j^{(i)} \right) \tag{1.7}$$

We shall note in section 3.

$$V = m_1, n_1; \dots; m_r, n_r; U = p_1, q_1; \dots; p_r, q_r \tag{1.8}$$

$$\mathbf{A} = [(a_j; \alpha_j^{(1)}, \dots, \alpha_j^{(r)}; A_j)]_{1,p}; \mathbf{B} = [(b_j; \beta_j^{(1)}, \dots, \beta_j^{(r)}; B_j)]_{1,q} \tag{1.9}$$

$$E = (e_j; u_j^{(1)} g_j^{(1)}, \dots, u_j^{(r)} g_j^{(r)}; E_j)_{1,R}; L = (f_j; U_j^{(1)} f_j^{(1)}, \dots, U_j^{(r)} f_j^{(r)}; L_j)_{1,R} \tag{1.10}$$

$$U = [(c_j^{(1)}, \gamma_j^{(1)}; C_j^{(1)})]_{1,p_1}; \dots; [(c_j^{(r)}, \gamma_j^{(r)}; C_j^{(r)})]_{1,p_r}; B = [(d_j^{(1)}, \delta_j^{(1)}; D_j^{(1)})]_{1,q_1}; \dots; [(d_j^{(r)}, \delta_j^{(r)}; D_j^{(r)})]_{1,q_r} \tag{1.11}$$

The multidimensional Laguerre transform is defined as follows, (see Chandel and Chauhan [3]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{\alpha, \beta, m} \{ \} = \frac{(-)^m m! \Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right)}{\Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \prod_{i=1}^n \Gamma(\gamma_i)} \int_0^\infty \dots \int_0^\infty e^{-\sum_{i=1}^n x_i} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right)^\beta \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{\gamma_i-1} L_m^{(\alpha)}\left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right) \{ \} dx_1 \dots dx_n \tag{1.12}$$

where $\text{Re}\left(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) > 0$, m, n are arbitrary positive integers, $\text{Re}(\gamma_i) > 0$, ($i = 1, \dots, n$)

Chandel and Chauhan [3] have introduced the following multidimensional Laguerre transform :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{\beta_i; \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K} \{ \} = K \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{(-)^{n_j} n_j! \Gamma(\gamma_j - \beta_j - n_j)}{\Gamma(\gamma_j - \beta_j) \Gamma(\gamma_j)} \int_0^\infty \dots \int_0^\infty e^{-\left(\sum_{i,j=1}^n \alpha_i^j x_i\right)} \prod_{j=1}^n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^j x_i\right)^{\beta_j} L_{n_j}^{\beta_j}\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^j x_i\right) \{ \} dx_1 \dots dx_n \tag{1.13}$$

provided

$$\text{Re}(\gamma_i), \text{Re}(\gamma_i - \beta_i - n_i) > 0, n_i \in \mathbf{N}; (i = 1, \dots, n) \text{ and } K = \begin{vmatrix} \alpha_1^1 & \dots & \alpha_n^1 \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \alpha_1^n & \dots & \alpha_n^n \end{vmatrix} \neq 0$$

2. Required Results :

In this section, we shall see several lemmas

Lemma 1 : (Chandel and Chauhan [3, p. 60, Eq. (2.2)]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)}(x_1^{m_1}, \dots, x_n^{m_n}) = \frac{\left(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i) m_i}{\left(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i} \quad (2.1)$$

Lemma 2 : $L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)}(1) = 1.$ (2.2)

If $\alpha = \beta$, we the following relation.

Lemma 3 : (Chandel and Chauhan [3, p. 61, Eq. (3.1)]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \alpha, m)}(x_1^{m_1}, \dots, x_n^{m_n}) = \frac{\left(\alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i) m_i}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i - m\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i} \quad (2.3)$$

Lemma 4 : (Chandel and Chauhan [3, p. 65, Eq. (4.3)]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)}\left(x_1^{m_1 \zeta_1} \dots x_n^{m_n \zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \eta_i\right) = \frac{\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i - \alpha\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (\zeta_i + \eta_i) \left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (\zeta_i + \eta_i) \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i) m_i \zeta_i}{\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i - \alpha - m\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (\zeta_i + \eta_i) \left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (\zeta_i + \eta_i)} \quad (2.4)$$

Lemma 5 : (Chandel and Chauhan [3, p. 68, Eq. (6.2)]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n, K)}\{1\} = 1 \quad (2.5)$$

Lemma 6 : (Chandel and Chauhan [3, p. 68, Eq. (6.3)]).

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{m_1} \dots \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{m_n} \right\} = K \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(\gamma_i - \beta_i)_{m_i} (\gamma_i)_{m_i}}{(\gamma_i - \beta_i - n_i)_{m_i}} \quad (2.6)$$

3. Main Results :

In the following we will consider the modified of generalized $\bar{A}$ -function of n variables.

Theorem 1 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ \bar{A} \left(\begin{matrix} u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \end{matrix} \right) \right\} = \frac{\Gamma(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i) \Gamma(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i)}{\Gamma(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i) \Gamma(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i) \prod_{i=1}^n \Gamma(\gamma_i)}$$

$$\bar{A}_{P+2, Q+2; R: U+1}^{-M, N+2; R': V+1} \left(\begin{matrix} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{matrix} \middle| \begin{matrix} \left(1 + \alpha - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \\ \mathbf{B}, \left(1 + \alpha + m - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \\ \left(1 - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \mathbf{A} : E : \mathbf{U}_n \\ \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n; 1 \right) : L : \mathbf{B} \end{matrix} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U}_n = (1 - \gamma_1, \zeta_1; 1), [(c_j^{(1)}, \gamma_j^{(1)}; C_j^{(1)})]_{1, p_1}, \dots, (1 - \gamma_n, \zeta_n; 1), [(c_j^{(n)}, \gamma_j^{(n)}; C_j^{(n)})]_{1, p_n} \quad (3.2)$$

$$V + 1 = m_1, n_1 + 1; \dots; m_n, n'_n + 1; U + 1 = p_1 + 1, q_1; \dots; p_n + 1, q_n \quad (3.3)$$

provided $\zeta_i, \eta_i, \text{Re}(\gamma_i) > 0 (i = 1, \dots, n)$, m is a positive integers and $|\arg(\Omega_i)u_i| < \frac{1}{2} \eta_i \pi$, Ω_i and η_i are defined by (1.5) and (1.7) respectively.

Proof : To prove the above result, expressing the modified of generalized multi-variable $\bar{A}$ -function in terms of multiple Mellin-Barnes contour integrals with the help of (1.1), we obtain (L.H.S)

$$\text{L.H.S} = L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ \bar{A} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \end{pmatrix} \right\} = L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} x_i^{\zeta_i s_i} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_i s_i} \right\} ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (3.5)$$

The multidimensional Laguerre is a multiple $(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ -integrals, now interchanging the order of $(s_1, \dots, s_n)$ -integrals and $(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ -integrals which is permissible under the stated conditions. The left hand side writes

$$\text{L.H.S} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left[\prod_{j=1}^n x_j^{\zeta_j s_j} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_j s_j} \right] ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (3.6)$$

Now, we use the lemma 4, we obtain

$$\text{L.H.S} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} \frac{\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i - \alpha \right) \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \eta_i) s_i \left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \right) \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \eta_i) s_i \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i) \zeta_i s_i}{\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i - \alpha - m \right) \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \eta_i) s_i \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \right) \sum_{i=1}^n (\zeta_i + \eta_i) s_i} ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (3.7)$$

using the following relation, $(a)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)}$, where $a \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$. And reinter-

preting the multiple Mellin-Barnes contour integrals in terms of modified of generalized $\bar{A}$ -function of n -variables, we have the desired result.

Theorem 2 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n; \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \bar{A} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{\zeta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{\zeta_n} \end{pmatrix} \right\} = K \bar{A}_{P, Q; R: U_2, 1}^{M, N; R': V+2} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 & \text{A} : E : U'_n \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ u_n & \text{B} : L : B_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$U'_n = (1 - \gamma_1 + \beta_1, \zeta_1; 1), (1 - \gamma_1, \zeta_1; 1) [(c_j^{(1)}, \gamma_j^{(1)}; C_j^{(1)})]_{1, n_1}; \dots; (1 - \gamma_n + \beta_n, \zeta_n; 1), (1 - \gamma_n, \zeta_n; 1) [(c_j^{(n)}, \gamma_j^{(n)}; C_j^{(n)})]_{1, p_n} \quad (3.9)$$

$$V + 2 = m_1, n_1 + 2; \dots; m_n, n'_n + 2; U_{2,1} = p_1 + 2, q_1 + 1; \dots; p_n + 2, q_n + 1 \quad (3.10)$$

$$B_n = [(d_j^{(1)}, \delta_j^{(1)}; D_j^{(1)})]_{1, q_1}, (1 - \gamma_1 + \beta_1 + \eta_1; \zeta_1; 1); \dots; [(d_j^{(n)}, \delta_j^{(n)}; D_j^{(n)})]_{1, q_n}, (1 - \gamma_n + \beta_n + \eta_n; \zeta_n; 1) \quad (3.11)$$

provided

$$\text{Re}(\gamma_i), \text{Re}(\gamma_i - \beta_i - \eta_i) > 0, \eta_i \in \mathbf{N}; (i = 1, \dots, n) \text{ and } |\arg(\Omega_i)u_i| < \frac{1}{2} \eta_i \pi \quad (3.12)$$

Proof : To prove the above result, expressing the modified of generalized multi-variable $\bar{A}$ -function in terms of multiple Mellin-Barnes contour integrals with the help of (1.1), we obtain (L.H.S)

$$\text{L.H.S} = L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n; \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \bar{A} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \end{pmatrix} \right\} = L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n; \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} \left\{ \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{\zeta_1 s_1} \dots \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{\zeta_n s_n} \right\} ds_1 \dots ds_n \right\} \quad (3.13)$$

The multidimensional Laguerre is a multiple $(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ -integrals, now interchanging the order of $(s_1, \dots, s_n)$ -integrals and $(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ -integrals which is permissible under the stated conditions. The left hand side is given by

$$\text{L.H.S} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} \\ L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n, K)} \left\{ \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{\zeta_1 s_1} \dots \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{\zeta_n s_n} \right\} ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (3.14)$$

Now, we use the lemma 6, we obtain

$$\text{L.H.S} = \frac{K}{(2\pi\omega)^n} \int_{L_1} \dots \int_{L_n} \phi(s_1, \dots, s_n) \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_i(s_i) u_i^{s_i} \frac{(\gamma_i - \beta_i)^{\zeta_i s_i} (\gamma_i)^{\zeta_i s_i}}{(\gamma_i - \beta_i - \eta_i)^{\zeta_i s_i}} ds_1 \dots ds_n \quad (3.15)$$

using the following relation, $(a)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)}$, where $a \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$. And reinter-

preting the multiple Mellin-Barnes contour integrals in terms of the modified of generalized $\bar{A}$ -function of n -variables, we have the desired result.

In the following section, we shall see several corollaries.

4. Special Cases :

In this section, the quantities $A_1, \mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{U}_{n,1}, B_1, \mathbf{B}_1, E_1, L_1, \mathbf{B}_{n,1}$ and $\mathbf{B}_1$ coincide respectively at the quantities $A, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{U}_n, B, \mathbf{B}, E, L, \mathbf{B}_n$ and $\mathbf{B}$ with the exponents are equal to 1.

If $E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$, we obtain the generalized of multivariable $\mathbf{A}$ -function and we have :

Corollary 1 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ A \begin{matrix} \left(u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \right) \\ \vdots \\ \left(u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \right) \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{\Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right)}{\Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \prod_{i=1}^n \Gamma(\gamma_i)}$$

$$A_{P+2, Q+2; U+1}^{M, N+2; V+1} \left(\begin{array}{c} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} \left(1 + \alpha - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \\ \mathbf{B}, \left(1 + \alpha + m - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \\ \left(1 - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n; 1 \right), \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{U}_n \\ \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n; 1 \right) : \mathbf{B} \end{array} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

under the conditions (3.1) and the conditions : $E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$.

Corollary 2 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ A \left(\begin{array}{c} u_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{\zeta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{\zeta_n} \end{array} \right) \right\} = K A_{P, Q; U, 2, 1}^{M, N+2; V+2} \left(\begin{array}{c} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{U}'_n \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{B} : \mathbf{B}_n \end{array} \right) \quad (4.2)$$

under the conditions (3.8) and the conditions cited above the corollary 1.

If $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$, we have the modified of multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function and :

Corollary 3 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ \bar{A} \left(\begin{array}{c} u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \end{array} \right) \right\} = \frac{\Gamma(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i) \Gamma\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right)}{\Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \prod_{i=1}^n \Gamma(\gamma_i)}$$

$$\bar{A}_{P+2, Q+2; R; U}^{M, N+2; R'; V+1} \left(\begin{array}{c} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} \left(1 + \alpha - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \\ \mathbf{B}_1, \left(1 + \alpha + m - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \end{array} \right)$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \left(1 - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \mathbf{A}_1; E_1; \mathbf{U}_{n,1} \\ \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \right); L_1; \mathbf{B}_1 \end{array} \right) \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U}_{n,1} = (1 - \gamma_1, \zeta_1), [(c_j^{(1)}, \gamma_j^{(1)})]_{1,p_1}, \dots, (1 - \gamma_n, \zeta_n), [(c_j^{(n)}, \gamma_j^{(n)})]_{1,p_n} \quad (4.4)$$

and

$$\mathbf{B}_1 = [(d_j^{(1)}, \delta_j^{(1)})]_{1,p_1}, \dots, [(d_j^{(n)}, \delta_j^{(n)})]_{1,p_n} \quad (4.5)$$

under the conditions (3.1) and the conditions : $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$.

Corollary 4 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \bar{A} \left(\begin{array}{l} u_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right) \zeta_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right) \zeta_n \end{array} \right) \right\} = K \bar{A}_{P,Q;|R:U_{2,1}}^{M,N;|R':V+2} \left(\begin{array}{l} u_1 \mid \mathbf{A}_1; E_1; \mathbf{U}'_{n,1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n \mid \mathbf{B}_1; L_1; \mathbf{B}_{n,1} \end{array} \right) \quad (4.6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}'_{n,1} &= (1 - \gamma_1 + \beta_1, \zeta_1), (1 - \gamma_1, \zeta_1), [(c_j^{(1)}, \gamma_j^{(1)})]_{1,n_1}; \dots; \\ &(1 - \gamma_n + \beta_n, \zeta_n), (1 - \gamma_n, \zeta_n), [(c_j^{(n)}, \gamma_j^{(n)})]_{1,p_n} \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

$$V+2 = m_1, n_1 + 2; \dots; m_n, n'_n + 2; \dots; U_{2,1} = p_1 + 2, q_1 + 1; \dots; p_n + 2, q_n + 1 \quad (4.8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B}_{n,1} &= [(d_j^{(1)}, \delta_j^{(1)})]_{1,q_1}, (1 - \gamma_1 + \beta_1 + \eta_1; \zeta_1); \dots; \\ &[(d_j^{(n)}, \delta_j^{(n)})]_{1,q_n}, (1 - \gamma_n + \beta_n + \eta_n; \zeta_n) \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

under the conditions (3.8) and $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$.

Now, we suppose $E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$ and $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$. Our function reduces to multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function defined by Gautam et al. [4] and we have:

Corollary 5 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\alpha, \beta, m)} \left\{ A \begin{pmatrix} u_1 x_1^{\zeta_1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n x_n^{\zeta_n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{\eta_n} \end{pmatrix} \right\} = \frac{\Gamma(\beta - \alpha - m + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i) \Gamma\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right)}{\Gamma\left(\beta - \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \Gamma\left(\beta + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i\right) \prod_{i=1}^n \Gamma(\gamma_i)}$$

$$A_{P+2, Q+2: U}^{M, N+2: V+1} \left(\begin{array}{l} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} \left(1 + \alpha - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \\ \mathbf{B}, \left(1 + \alpha + m - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \\ \left(1 - \beta - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1 + \eta_1, \dots, \zeta_n + \eta_n \right), \mathbf{A} : \mathbf{U}_{n,1} \\ \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i; \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \right) : \mathbf{B}_1 \end{array} \right) \quad (4.10)$$

under the conditions (3.1) and the conditions : $E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$ and $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$.

Corollary 6 :

$$L_{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_n}^{(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n; \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n; K)} \left\{ \mathfrak{K} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^1 x_i \right)^{\zeta_1} \\ \vdots \\ u_n \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i^n x_i \right)^{\zeta_n} \end{pmatrix} \right\} = K A_{P, Q: R: U_{2,1}}^{-M, N: R': V+2} \left(\begin{array}{l} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_n \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{A}_1 : \mathbf{U}'_{n,1} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{B}_1 : \mathbf{B}_{n,1} \end{array} \right) \quad (4.11)$$

under the conditions (3.8) and : $E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$ and $A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$.

Remarks :

We obtain the same multidimensional Laguerre Transform formulas with the multivariable I -function defined by Prathima et al. [7], (see also Sreenivas [10-12] and Sunitha [15-16] if $(\alpha_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)}, \gamma_j^{(i)}, \delta_j^{(i)}) \in \mathbf{R}$ and $M = E_i = L_j = R = R' = 0$), the modified

multivariable defined by Prasad and Singh [6] if $(A_j = B_j = E_j = L_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1, \alpha_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)}, \gamma_j^{(i)}, \delta_j^{(i)}, g_j^{(i)}, f_j^{(i)} \in \mathbf{R}$ and $M = 0$), the multivariable H -function defined by Srivastava and Panda [13-14] if $(M = E_j = L_j = R = R' = 0, A_j = B_j = C_j^{(i)} = D_j^{(i)} = 1$ and $\alpha_j^{(i)}, \beta_j^{(i)}, \gamma_j^{(i)}, \delta_j^{(i)} \in \mathbf{R}$) see Chandel and Chauhan [3] for more precisions.

We obtain the same multiple integrals transformation formulas about the multivariable Gimel function defined by Ayant [2], the multivariable I -function defined by Prasad [5] and the multivariable Aleph-function defined by Ayant [1].

By the following similar procedure, the results of this document can be extended to product of any finite number of modified of generalized multivariable $\bar{A}$ -functions.

5. Conclusion :

The importance of our all the results lies in their manifold generality. Firstly, in view of the unified multiple integrals with general arguments utilized in this study, we can obtain a large variety of infinite multiple, double and single integrals. Secondly by specializing the various parameters as well as variables in the modified of generalized multivariable $\bar{A}$ -function, we get a big number of infinite integrals involving remarkably wide variety of useful special functions (or product of such functions) which are expressible in terms of E, F, G, H, I , simpler special functions of one and several variables. Hence the formulae derived in this paper are most general in character and may prove to be useful in several interesting cases appearing in literature of Pure and Applied Mathematics and Mathematical Physics.

References :

- [1] F.Y. Ayant : A Fractional Integration of the Product of Two Multivariable Aleph-Functions and a General Class of Polynomials I, Int. Jr. of Mathematical Sciences & Applications, 7(2) (2017), 181-198.
- [2] F.Y. Ayant : Some transformations and identities form multivariable Gimel-function, International Journal of Mathematics and Technology (IJMTT), 59(4) (2018), 248-255.

- [3] R.C. Chandel and S.S. Chauhan : Multidimensional Laguerre transforms, Jour. Pure Math. 20 (2003), 59-72.
- [4] B.P. Gautam, A.S. Asgar and A.N Goyal : On the multivariable A -function. Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika, Vol. 29(4) 1986, page 67-81.
- [5] Y.N. Prasad : Multivariable I -function, Vijnana Parishad Anusandhan Patrika, 29 (1986), 231-237.
- [6] Y.N. Prasad and A.K. Singh : Basic properties of the transform involving and H -function of r -variables as kernel. Indian Acad Math, No 2, 1982, page 109-115.
- [7] J. Prathima, V. Nambisan and S.K. Kurumujji : A Study of I -function of Several Complex Variables, International Journal of Engineering Mathematics, (2014), 1-12.
- [8] J. Prathima and Vasudevan : Multiple Integral Transforms Involving I -Function of Several Complex Variables, Journal of Inequalities and Special Functions (Ilirias), 5(1), (2014), 13-20.
- [9] J. Prathima and Vasudevan : Multidimensional integral transform involving I -function of several complex variables as kernel, IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM), 10(2), (2014), 73-80.
- [10] P.C. Sreenivas and M. Sunitha : On Fourier Series of I -Functions of r -Variables, International J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls. (IJMSEA), 11(2), (2017), 193-205.
- [11] P.C. Sreenivas, T.M. Vasudevan Nambisan and M. Sunitha : On Expansion Formulae Involving Multivariable I -functions, International J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls. (IJMSEA), 11(2), (2017), 39-45.
- [12] P.C. Sreenivas, T.M. Vasudevan Nambisan and M. Sunitha : On Summation Formulae Involving Multivariable I -functions, International J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls. (IJMSEA), 10(3), (2016), 91-97.

- [13] H.M. Srivastava and R. Panda : Some expansion theorems and generating relations for the H -function of several complex variables, Comment. Math. Univ. St. Paul. 24(1975), page 119-137.
- [14] H.M. Srivastava and R. Panda : Some expansion theorems and generating relations for the H -function of several complex variables II. Comment. Math. Univ. St. Paul. 25(1976), page 167-197.
- [15] M. Sunitha , P.C. Sreenivas and T.M. Vasudevan Nambisan : An Integral Involving The Product of an Incomplete Gamma Function, Generalized Struve's Function and I -Function of r -Variables, International J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls. (IJMSEA), 11(3), (2017), 179-184.
- [16] M. Sunitha , P.C. Sreenivas and T.M. Vasudevan Nambisan : On The r -Integrals Involving The I -Functions of Several Variables, International J. of Math. Sci. & Engg. Appls. (IJMSEA), 12(2), (2018), 35-42.